

Induction Motor Control and Protection Using IOT*

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Abstract:- Control and protection of an electric component system is highly important in any sector. This concept proposes employing wireless technology to run an ac motor for the needed purpose. To get the necessary output, we used an Arduino microcontroller that is connected to a motor driver. We utilise an Android application that connects to the WIFI modem of the control circuit that is connected to the motor over the internet. The microcontroller is connected to the WIFI modem. The order is received by the WIFI modem through the internet via the mobile phone app. The signal is sent to the Microcontroller via the WIFI modem. The signal is decoded by the microcontroller and sent to the appropriate relays. The relays then switch between high voltage, low voltage, and over current. As a result, this project.

Keywords:- Internet of Things , IOT , Induction Motor, TRIAC, Arduino.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machines systems are preferred driven by electric motors in today's developing industries. AC Because of the simpler rotor structure, induction motors are low-cost and need little maintenance. Induction motors also have a high power factor, are small and compact, are durable, and are less expensive. An induction motor offers the advantages of superior speed control, long-term overload capacity, and strong beginning torque. As a result, induction motors are employed in industries, crane elevators, residential, and farm motors.

The Internet of Things (IOT) has received much attention as a technology that has accelerated current wireless communication innovations. For the most part, it has a lot of advantages. The Internet of Things (IoT) is lending a hand in achieving industrial automation via remote access. IoT devices that make up a system can connect with other devices on the Commman platform. As a result of this system, important data and numerous other parameters information are exchanged across devices in order to optimise their performance. This prototype exhibited IOT-based Induction motor monitoring parameters such as voltage, current, and speed using a sensor and cloud, and managing the speed of the induction motor using TRIAC control since its speed can be readily changed by altering the supply voltage. The project's major goal is to develop a low-cost, effective protection system for induction motors. The protective system should guard against undervoltage and overvoltage. The sustainability of production in industries can be maintained by continuously monitoring the parameters, and

the production of industry may be improved by using more efficient motors. Detect any problems that occur in the induction motor.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The majority of the project work was done in the field of induction motor control and protection to regulate different induction motor parameters. [1] suggested utilising an ATmega328 microprocessor to automate and monitor induction motors. Overcurrent single phasing is protected by the microcontroller. [2] shows a PIC microcontroller-based control system that protects single-phase motors from undervoltage, overvoltage, and overheating, as well as measuring motor speed. However, the PIC microcontroller's programme is long and has a complicated structure. [3] presents a review paper on a microprocessor-based control system for a three-phase induction motor fed by a PWM IGBT inverter. A complexity issue emerges here as well. [4] presents a technique for obtaining a time-protection model for an induction motor from voltage imbalance. The approach is based on the thermal impact of mechanical overloads and voltage imbalance conditions on the motor. [5] Multilevel inverters employ the Phase-shifting Pulse width Modulation (PSPWM) approach, whereas induction motors use the Space Vector Modulation Strategy (SVM). [6] used a PIC 16C84 microcontroller to build a system. [7] We have examined a system that uses an Arduino microcontroller to monitor metrics like as speed, temperature, current, and voltage. This necessitates the use of extra motors. The suggested method is a sensor-based technology [8] that is implemented using a PLC.

Multiple researches on different control and protection systems for Single Phase Induction Motors have been undertaken [9][10]. As a result, there are limited studies on IoT-based Induction Motor Control and Protection [13][14]. Using the most recent IOT[11], we suggested this system for parameter control and protection of induction motors. There is a downside of complicated structure in GSM, PLC, and PIC Microcontroller[12] by completing Research scope by Analyzing literature study. With the usage of GSM, there is a restricted pace of data transfer, as well as a considerable amount of electromagnetic radiation. This can be solved by IOT, which reduces human labor and work while also transferring data at a high rate and providing personal safety and security. A speed control approach based on TRIAC is used.

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As a result, the induction motor will need to be controlled and protected in the future. However, there is an issue with the speed control approach, as well as an efficient protection strategy for other parameters. Which was fixed by using an IoT-based protection system that increased dependability. Additionally uses an android application to check parameters 24 hours a day. Been programmed to act as a Flash drive converter.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Fig 1 shows a block schematic of the proposed system. It motor, and a Relay Driver Circuit. The voltage sensor, IoT module, and LCD display are all wired directly to the Arduino UNO. Relay driver circuit connects capacitor start induction motor to Arduino UNO. The TRIAC is utilised to control the motor's speed. We can control the motor with the Blynk app on Android.

Fig.1 System Block Diagram Hardware Description

1) Arduino UNO

The Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328. On this board, there are 14 digital input/output pins (six of which are PWM outputs), six analogue inputs, a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power connector, a Hdmi port, and a reset button. It includes everything you'll need to get started with the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer through USB or use an AC-to-DC converter or battery to power it. The Uno is different from prior boards in that it does not use the FTDI Flash driver chip. Instead, an Atmega8U2 is used, which has been programmed to act as a Flash drive converter.

Speed controller is made up of an Arduino uno, an LCD display, an IoT module, a voltage sensor, a supply, a TRIAC, a capacitor-start induction is a low-cost, miniature display. Because of the integrated controller, dealing with a microcontroller is simple (the black blob on the back of the board). This is a standard controller included on many screens (HD 44780).

2) 16x2 LCD

An LCD is a low-cost, miniature display. Because of the integrated controller, dealing with a microcontroller is simple (the black blob on the back of the board). This is a standard controller included on many screens (HD 44780).

Features

- 5 x 8 dots with cursor
- Built-in controller (KS 0066 or Equivalent)
- + 5V power supply (Also available for + 3V)
- 1/16 duty cycle
- B/L to be driven by pin 1, pin 2 or pin 15, pin 16 or A.K (LED)
- N.V. optional for + 3V power supply

Fig.3 LCD

3) An LCD

Fig.2 Arduino

3) speed controller

The TRIAC speed-control circuit for induction motors illustrated in FIG. 4 is similar to the universal motor speed-control circuit displayed. To delay the phase of the gate trigger, the circuit in FIG. 4 uses a single-time-constant circuit. Because induction motors cannot be slowed down enough to enter the difficult hysteresis area for which the double-time-constant gate circuit is required, this simpler technique is permitted. This speed-control circuit is appropriate for induction motors with permanent split capacitors. This control method is also applicable to shaded-

pole induction motors. When the load is a fan or blower, this speed-control approach works well with any type of induction motor.

4) IOT Module

Fig.5 ESP2866 IOT Module

The ESP8266 WIFI Module is a self-contained SOC with an integrated TCP/IP internet protocol suite that allows any microcontroller to connect to your WIFI network. The ESP8266 may run a programme or off-load all Wi-Fi networking tasks to another processor. This module comes with AT instructions firmware, which allows you to get capabilities comparable to an Arduino WIFI shield; however, you may load different firmwares to generate your own programme on the module's memory and CPU. This module has an inherent low-power 32-bit CPU running at 80 MHz that may be used for custom firmware. This also means that small website may be hosted without the use of a controller. The ESP8266 features an identity RF and supports APSD and Bluetooth co-existence interfaces for VoIP applications.

Circuit Diagram Description

Fig.6 Circuit Diagram

The circuit diagram of an induction motor's protection and control system is shown in Figure 5. The diagram above depicts the connections between various sections of the system that receive 12 volt dc power from the power supply system portion. The power supply part has a 12v/2A transformer that converts 230 volts to 12 volts. A bridge rectifier is used to convert AC to DC. A 2200 mf capacitor is employed to smooth the output. The LM317 voltage regulator is used to obtain a 12 volt dc continuous supply.

Fig.4 TRIAC Speed Control

FIG.4 Induction motor speed control using a TRIAC circuit. RCA is the manufacturer of this product. (A. Components for two different line voltages are shown in a schematic design.) M. B.)

Under some circumstances, TRIAC control of resistance-start and capacitor-start induction motors is possible. In most cases, the speed-control range must be limited; the speed should not be decreased to the point where the centrifugal switch reconnects the beginning winding or capacitor. All things considered, the permanent split-capacitor motor will provide the greatest range of speed control. There is no centrifugal switch on this type of induction motor. It also works effectively in a high-slip environment.

When the load is resistive, as it is with lights or heaters, the RC "snubbing network" linked across the TRIAC does not normally show in the circuit. TRIAC turn-off will occur at zero current due to the inductive nature of a motor load, but the voltage across the TRIAC will not be zero at that moment. Despite the lack of a gate signal, a voltage step is created across the TRIAC, which might result in retriggering. Even though the TRIAC's voltage-blocking capabilities surpasses peak ac voltage by a significant margin, this can happen. It's not the amplitude of the voltage step, or "spike," that's the problem, but the rate at which it changes.

The Arduino is powered by a 12 volt DC source. It has 14 input/output pins and 6 digital input/output pins. The ground and VCC pins of the IOT module are linked to the 0 pin of the Arduino's I/O pin, while VCC is attached to the 1 pin. The operation of the LCD is divided into three parts. 1) pins for power and 2) pins for control 3) Pins for data. There are three supply pins, one of which is grounded. The 2nd and 3 pins are connected to a potentiometer, which adjusts the LCD's contrast. The 4 and 6 control pins are connected to an Arduino, which controls the data. The 5th control pin is connected to the ground. We utilise a four-bit LCD. The Arduino I/O pins are linked to four data pins. The voltage sensor is attached to the Arduino's A4 pin. Through R2 and LED, the A0 pin is linked to the optocoupler. Through a resistor, the A1 pin is linked to the zero crossing detection circuit. Because we can't connect the motor directly to the Arduino, we created a relay driver circuit as well as a TRIAC controller circuit to regulate the motor's speed. The optocoupler in the TRIAC controller circuit provides a gate pulse to initiate the TRIAC. TRIAC is also linked to a zero crossing detection circuit. The motor receives the main supply's neutral as well as phase through TRIAC. The Arduino UNO is programmed with the necessary code to control the motor.

IV. HARDWARE SETUP

Hardware setup consist of Arduino uno ,LCD display, IOT module ,Voltage sensor ,supply ,TRIAC ,capacitor start induction motor , relay driver circuit. Voltage sensor , IOT module and LCD display is directly connected to Arduino uno .Capacitor start induction motor is connected Arduino through relay driver circuit .TRIAC is used for speed control of motor .We can operate motor from blynk app

Fig.7 Hardware Setup

V. RESULT

1. Under Voltage

If supply voltage of Induction motor is less than 260 v then fault under voltage is detected and motor stop running

Fig.8 undervoltage on kit display

Fig.9 Undervoltage Notification

2. Overvoltage

If supply voltage is more than 260 v then fault over-voltage is detected and motor turns off

Fig.10 overvoltage Notification

3. Speed Measurement
1. 0% Speed applied

Fig.11 Speed measurement 1 on kit display

Fig.13 Speed measurement 2 Notification

Fig.11 Speed measurement 1 notification

3.100% Speed applied

Fig.14 Speed measurement 3 on kit display

Fig.15 Speed measurement 3 Notification

1. When 50% speed applied

Fig.12 Speed measurement 2 on kit display

From observations or result. This system will protect the motor from several faults such as undervoltage, overvoltage and circuit will switch on motor under safety conditions . It Display all results on kit display as well as mobile phone . when fault occurs it sends notification to user also measures speed of induction motor accurately. It improves motor performance and make it reliable and increases its life.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper represents the IOT is well known and most rapidly growing nowadays. Now IOT is becoming an integral aspect of human life. In the future, many items will be connected to the cloud. IOT has recently gained ground into fields such as industry, home, automation, medical field etc. With help of controllers, sensors this prototype gives IOT based condition monitoring parameters and controlling the speed of motor with help of TRIAC. Visualize and analysis voltage parameters on a LCD display. By analyzing motor parameters make the motor to be operated in protective and safe in nature, It also helps in calculating a new data to interact with social media and other gadgets from blynk app, We operate motor parameters on mobile application by connecting to hotspot module. Through blynk app continuously monitored the motor parameters and if fault takes place it will get alert notification on android application. In industries required monitoring data value for maintenance and power consumption. In case the motor gets overvoltage, undervoltage than its rated value it will get automatically disconnected from supply and motor gets off.

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